

Employer Information Requirements (EIR) for Geometric survey with aerial and terrestrial documentation techniques

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The Project **Urban PERISCOPE** INTEGRATED/0918/0034 is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

Abstract

This document is intended for incorporation by reference in UP Geometric survey working group for the documentation with laser scan and aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry techniques, for as-built conditions of the 20 buildings selected (10 buildings in the Old Strovolos core district, Nicosia and 10 buildings in the Cami Cedid and Arnaut districts, Limassol) to function as testbeds for the development of the UP platform will be created as central models to be hosted on an open source BIM software by means of importing and updating the data generated in T4.3 (WP4). The guide has been prepared to assist the UP-project team ensuring quality in 3D geometrical survey data. It provides guidelines for the solicitation of Geometric survey documentation techniques services and evaluation criteria to ensure that the specified requirements for the deliverables are met.

Furthermore, the purpose of this document is to record the recommended quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) process required to streamline the procurement and acceptance of 3D laser scanned (imaging) data and photogrammetric data and their derived deliverables. The Geometrical data survey is to be used as an appendix to the base Scan to BIM.

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Scan –to-BIM OVERVIEW

The geometric survey phases for the entire life cycle of a structure were identified as shown in *figure 1*. The proposed Scan-to-BIM workflow is oriented towards a BIM application that is implemented using the generated As-is BIM. To ensure that the generated as-is BIM satisfies the requirements of the intended BIM application, the Scan-to-BIM process is performed in four steps including 1. Identification of information requirements, 2. Determination of required scan data quality, 3. Scan data acquisition, and 4. As-is BIM reconstruction. The four steps and their relationships are further explained in the following subsections.

Figure 1 – The proposed workflow oriented Scan-to-BIM framework

1.2 Scope

This Guide establishes recommendations that can be continually shared and agreed upon by the stakeholders and the UP Project geometric survey team. The scope of this guide is to support the implementation of Geometric survey with aerial and terrestrial documentation techniques by the UP team.

PROJECT PHASING

The Employer Information Requirements (EIR) for Geometrical data survey document applies to all phases of the project planning, system calibration, data collection, processing, modelling and creation of final deliverables. It is the geometrical survey project's team responsibility to certify that the methods proposed will produce the desired results and that they are in compliance with this Geometrical data survey document.

This guide is structured in two parts based on the BIM Technical Standards: 3D Imaging.

Part 1 - Quality Assurance (QA), will refer to the overall planning procedures required to establish and maintain quality throughout the entire UP project. The QA process will take place prior to the start of the geometric survey of every heritage building.

Part 2 - Quality Control (QC), will refer to the procedures that commence with the fieldwork and continue to the point of final deliverables.

Figure 2 – Phase diagram

2.1 Phase 1: Project Planning Quality Assurance (PPQA)

The following diagram depicts a typical Project Planning template which shall outline the overall approach being taken to ensure that each phase of the subject project will meet the needs of the UP project. This plan will address, among other items, equipment selection, field procedures, Area of Interest (AOI), Items of Interest (IOI), staffing, security, data processing and final delivery. The UP team will outline the quality checks that will be performed during each phase of the project. The PPQA must include specific references related to hardware and software that are going to be used on the project.

Based on the Project planning diagram the UP Geometric survey working group shall complete and provide all the necessary information by fill in **Appendix 1** based on the following guidelines.

Figure 3 – Project Planning Diagram

PP2. Project Objectives

PP2.1 Statement of Intent

A statement of intent describes the intended use of the data to be acquired and processed. Establishing and recognizing the intended use of the data will help define the appropriate means and methods that should be used to acquire, process and check the data. This statement will also aid future users of the data to gain a better understanding of the suitability of the data for their intended use.

PP2.2 Level of Accuracy

A statement that describes the methods to be used to achieve the level of accuracy (LOA) as required in the project specifications. The level of accuracy for the UP project will be affected by a number of factors, including the inherent accuracy and calibration of the scanner; methods used for establishing the scanner location; cameras location; cameras lenses type; aerial or terrestrial photogrammetry equipment's; aerial or terrestrial photogrammetry path; survey control point; point density; registration methods used to combine scans or cameras; and mesh modeling of the data. The UP team must explain the intended procedure to be used to check the work in progress and the intended means used to demonstrate the accuracy achieved, both in the field and in the office.

PP3.1 Level of Detail

A. Scanning Level of Detail

Level of Detail	Tolerance mm	Minimum Artifact Size (resolution) mm x mm
Level 1	±51	152x152
Level 2	±13	25x25
Level 3	±6	13x13
Level 4	±3	13x13

Tolerance: The allowable dimensional deviation in the deliverable from truth (truth being a measurement obtained by some other means), in the specified coordinate frame. An example of tolerance is: Point cloud: the distance between two points in a point cloud as compared to the true distance between the same two points in the actual scene should be less than or equal to the specified tolerance.

Minimum Artifact Size: The dimensions of the smallest recognizable feature.

B. Model Level of Detail

When required to model from scan one of the following Level of Details will be required.

Level	Type	Suitable Down-Stream Use of Model
LOD100	Conceptual / Massing	Early pre-design efforts
LOD200	Approximate Geometry	Schematic Design / Design Development
LOD300	Precise Geometry	Construction Documents
LOD400	Fabrication Level*	Fabrication and Assembly
LOD500	As-Built	Record Drawings

*LOD400 is included only to maintain consistency in BIM standards and should never be listed as a scanning deliverable.

C. Deliverable Selection Matrix – Definitions

C1. Coordinate frame

A hierarchical system of scale in which each scan or photogrammetry is registered per the following criteria:

Level 1: Total project area. Coordinate Frame: Local coordinate frame (coordinate frame used by the local jurisdiction) or the State Plane Coordinate Frame. The control network should be tied to this coordinate frame.

Level 2: Subsection of Level 01 (e.g., building). Coordinate Frame: Local coordinate frame (coordinate frame used by the local jurisdiction) or project coordinate frame.

Level 3: Subsection of Level 02 (e.g., floor level). Coordinate Frame: Project coordinate frame or instrument coordinate frame.

Level 4: Subsection of Level 03 (e.g., room or artifact). Coordinate Frame: Instrument coordinate frame. There can be multiple Areas of Interest with common coordinate frames. For this, the following syntax applies: Level 1-A, Level 1-B, etc. Note that particularly small buildings, may only have one level of detail. For example, if the data can be obtained in one scan, then there is only one Level of detail, Level 1, and the coordinate frame is the instrument coordinate frame.

A control network is used for dimensional control and quality control. A project coordinate frame is a coordinate frame that is established by a service provider and is used as a frame of reference for all the data obtained in the project. The project coordinate frame should be tied to the control network. An instrument coordinate frame is local to the instrument. The origin of the instrument coordinate frame is the instrument center. For further information see GSA BIM Guide Series 03, Section 2.3.1 at <http://gsa.gov/bim>

C2. Deliverable Type

The service provider shall prepare and submit the deliverables in the formats listed below. One objective may require several deliverable types. The GSA PBS CAD standards apply for all cases of this deliverable. The PBS CAD standards can be found at the GSA website: <http://gsa.gov>

C.2.1 Type 1 - 2D Drawings

Type 1.1 = Plans

Type 1.2 = Sections

Type 1.3 = Elevations

Type 1.4 = Details

Submit in *.dwg format

C.2.2 Type 2 – 3D Models

Surface model must adhere to the GSA PBS CAD standards while object models must adhere to GSA BIM Guides found at <http://gsa.gov/bim> and GSA Region 5 BIM Standards.

Type 2.1 = Surface Model

Type 2.2 = Object Model.

Specifications of an object model may include component information (e.g., wall, column), relationships between components, space information (e.g., rooms), and attributes (e.g., wall material). In most cases scanning is done in preparation for a design and construction project. All model data is to be completed in a format which will support the goals of the design and construction project. (240320_PERISCOPE_SurveyDocument). Object Models must be created in a file format which is compatible with the needs of the project. Translations from non-native platforms are only permitted when the full fidelity of the object model is preserved.

C.2.3 Type 3 – Scan and Photogrammetry Data

Type 3.1 = Registered point cloud

Type 3.2 = Published point cloud data to a web-based viewing platform

Type 3.3 = Conversion of point cloud data to an ASCII format

The point cloud data shall be reduced in size, to filter noise and redundant data to the maximum extent possible without compromising the accuracy and resolution of the model.

C.2.3 Type 4 – Raw Scan and Photogrammetry Data

These data are the data from individual scans, terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry that have not been registered or filtered. In the case of scanning, the data is from a single scan as exported by the instrument software. While in the case of photogrammetry the raw images. At a minimum, the documentation for these files should contain the date of the scan, the location of the scan, the instrument used, the instrument settings, and operator name.

-Raw data for each scan in individual files.

-Raw data must be the original data from the instrument and not manipulated in any way.

-Digital photographs taken by the instrument (if applicable).

C.2.4 Type 5 – Presentation Data

The UP team shall submit a minimum of (10) presentation quality images, derived from the 3D scanning and photogrammetry process for the final submission. The images shall be a combination of overall areas (such as site, building, etc.) and concentrated areas showing elements such as ornamentation and walls in detail. They shall be high quality suitable for publication.

PP4. Equipment

It is the UP-working team's responsibility to ensure that all field equipment is calibrated and operating within manufacturer's specifications for the duration of the project. The UP-working group shall provide information related to 3d scan -type and model, equipment for terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry - model of camera, lenses, and rectified photography properties.

PP5. Data acquisition plan

The UP team will design a data acquisition strategy that outlines the field methods that will be employed to ensure that all necessary data will be collected at the required resolution and accuracy. A method for spot-checking the data in the field will be included. As part of the Data Acquisition Plan, a Scan Plan shall be submitted showing scanner locations, target locations, target heights and control traverses, the photogrammetry paths if required. In order to achieve the required accuracy, the UP team will need to consider how best to establish the appropriate level of survey control for the project. When a control network is required, it shall be established in conformity with the Federal Geodetic Control Committee Standards and Specifications. It is the UP team's sole responsibility to determine the level of control required and the procedures that need to be followed to achieve the desired level of accuracy. A Survey Control Report should detail: the methods used; the error of closure of the control traverse; how an open-end traverse was checked; and any information on the control monumentation, if it was made permanent.

PP6. Data processing

The UP team will outline the methodology used to post-process the data and check its integrity. These checks, including Registration Reports detailing the point cloud registration accuracies, a statistical comparison of the point cloud data, and screen shots comparing point cloud with the derived CAD models and/or BIM will be documented and included as part of the final deliverables.

PP7. Reference Materials

This section includes a list all existing information to be provided to the documentation survey for reference, such as existing building documentation, building preservation plans, environmental assessments/EIS reports, and/or other relevant surveys and studies etc.

2.2 Phase 2: Data Acquisition Quality control (DAQC)

The second phase marks the start of the Part 2 – Quality Control and involves the UP Team performing the initial field work to acquire the data as defined by the UP team. During this phase, the UP Team should submit, a *Data Acquisition Report - Appendix 2* - which documents all field data acquisition activities such as survey instrument, survey control and scan plan.

Figure 3 – Data Acquisition Quality control diagram

In detail, as part of the DAQC Plan, the UP team shall provide a structured approach for field technicians and document their methods of data acquisition in order to confirm they are complying with the Quality Management Program. These routines shall prescribe the means for field-testing acquired data to ensure the data being collected is accurate and trusted representation of the actual field conditions. The DAQC consists of the following parts:

DA1. Survey Instrument

A statement that establishes the methods that field personnel will use to ensure that all survey instruments used on the project are properly calibrated and working within the manufacturer’s specifications whenever data is being collected.

DA2. Survey Control

Control is accomplished by placing targets that have been located using standard survey control procedures (see previous section) within the Field of View (FOV) of the scanner or camera- in case of photogrammetry.

DA3. Survey plan

A careful review of the Survey Plan is an important part of the DAQC process. The Survey Plan will identify proposed scanner types, scanner locations and aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry equipment and paths. These notes shall serve to document the actual scanner locations, photogrammetry paths, as well as target locations, target IDs and target heights in sufficient detail to replicate the process for field validation of the data, should it be required. If a target becomes unusable because the RMS (Root-mean-square) error is too great, a cloud-to-cloud registration process may be acceptable. In such cases, it should be documented which targets were unusable, why they were

unusable and which scans relied upon a cloud-to-cloud registration process. It should also be noted that some technologies utilize feature recognition to capture and register scan data. In these instances, the traditional process of target placement may not be relevant. If scanning is based on targetless registration, sufficient documentation shall be provided such that the data capture can be replicated and checked by an independent third party. In the case of photogrammetry the first step is to gather multiple photos of the heritage asset from various angles. It is also necessary to gather extra information for reference, scale metric and correctly exposing the photos. The survey plan consists of the following parts:

DA3.1 Site Conditions

Prior to beginning the work, the Area of Interest (AOI) shall be evaluated to determine the best time to collect data. Attention must be paid to identify obstructions and to minimize excessive artifacts that may cast shadows and cause occlusions in the data. For exterior work, it is important to check the weather forecast for rain, snow, fog, smoke, or blowing dust as well as extreme temperatures that may affect the scanner's performance.

DA3.2 Location of geometric survey equipment

The following items should be considered when deciding where the geometric equipment optimally should be located. In addition, safety should always be taken into consideration when selecting setup locations.

A. Useful Range: The accuracy of scan data cannot rely on beyond its useful range. Point data from a scanner or photogrammetry will become more widely spaced as the distance from the geometric survey equipment increases and less "documenting" energy is returned. At a certain distance, the error will exceed acceptable standards and beyond that, no data will be returned. Consideration must be given to ensure that the data outside the useful range of the 3d documentation is not relied upon for the final deliverables. The useful range is determined by factors such as the individual documentation equipment's accuracy and range specifications as well as the accuracy requirements of the subject project.

B. Point Density: Choosing the proper point density is important since it not only impacts the density of the data, but also the speed at which the data is acquired and processed. If the point density specified is set too low, there may not be sufficient points captured to adequately model the Items of Interest (IOI). If the point density specified is set too high, the data acquisition time may be very long and may make working with the data set very difficult and could severely impact the performance of the computer used to process the data. The contractor shall also ensure that proper overlap of scans is achieved in order to comply with the point density specified for the project. It is recommended that the project's point spacing specification be compared to the performance specification of the laser scanner manufacturer in order to select the appropriate scanner resolution for the acquisition of the required point density.

C. Positioning: The 3D scanners are line-of-sight instruments. This makes the selection of geometric equipment's locations and proper positioning crucial to ensuring proper data capture and efficient processing of the data. Factors to consider when selecting a scan location in order to minimize error and/or noise in the data include: 1. The angle of incidence to the object; and, 2. environmental conditions. In the case of photogrammetry survey when shooting an object, it is important to have full coverage of it. All parts of the heritage building must be covered by several pictures so the reconstruction software can create groups of similar pixels, so that the final asset doesn't have holes or under sampled areas. The reconstruction software

needs to have enough similar pixels within the set of pictures to produce the point cloud. For a precise reconstruction it is recommended to have 70% - 80% overlap between pictures. Practically speaking it simply means that between each shot, should do a side step of around 30 centimeters and maintain the camera focus on the subjects, then do top to bottom pictures to cover the objects. Any movement when shooting will result in a blurry photograph.

DA3.3 Targets

The UP team shall use industry-accepted targets and follow the manufacturer's recommended spacing/distance for placement of targets. Targets should not be moved until scanning operations have been completed.

DA3.4 Color checker

A color checker must be used to white balance the photos, but also as a scale metric for the virtual asset. Knowing the size of reconstructed buildings is important as the photogrammetry process loses this information. The UP team should find a good location for the color checker. The color checker must be placed close enough to the subject, but it shouldn't be shadowed by it, and in a way that can be easily removed during the process, or digitally paint it out. Also, the colour checker should usually be facing the sky.

DA3.5 Scale metric

It is usually important to keep the same ratio between the real world and your reconstructed heritage assets, depending on the context of your game. To achieve this, it is required to have a reference object of a known size in the reconstructed mesh that can be used to define the scale. Any object can be used. The color checker is a good candidate as it is already located near the subject and includes a 5 cm ruler. In the case of heritage buildings, the UP team could measure a part of it so that you know the real-world scale.

DA3.6 Detail textures

Detail textures are a secondary layer of textures used in combination with the main texture to add detail at a different scale. For example, a building texture which covers a large area of a heritage building might be enhanced by adding a higher resolution detail texture at a much smaller scale which focuses on ornament elements. Scanned material can benefit from the same technique, scanning first at a coarse level, then performing a second detailed scan that can be combined. The capture process for detail textures is the same as for regular surfaces, except that shots are focused more closely on a small area. The area chosen to produce the details texture should be as generic as possible because detail textures are typically tiled many times across the object compared with the main texture. In practice, the shots are done at the closest autofocus limit. Figure 4 below shows on left the coarse subject, used to create the geometry and base material, and on the right the detailed area scanned to produce detail textures. During this phase, the UP Team should advise the *Detailed textures element list* - **Appendix 5** – in order to decide which elements should be captured with detailed texture.

Figure 4 – The correct distance from the subject for each purpose. Geometry: Global photos to capture the main shape of an object. Detail geometry/Material: Closer photos to bring more detail in the geometry and produce a usable material. Detail texture: Photos done close-up at the autofocus limit. Used to produce detail textures.

2.3 Phase 3: Data Processing

Once the completeness of the data has been verified in the field, the data can be transferred to the office for post-processing. The actual post-processes used will depend on the required final deliverables. Some common forms of deliverables may include registered point cloud data, 2D line work, 3D geometric models, BIM and/or other 3D imagery. Furthermore, in the case of photogrammetry survey, the photos need to be calibrated (white balanced), then sent to a reconstruction application. The reconstruction application compares the shapes in the photos (Alignment) to generate a high-resolution 3D mesh. The color contained in the pictures is then transferred to either the mesh's vertex colors (Colorize) or textures used on the surface of the mesh. A thorough review of the point cloud and mesh model data is critical to ensure the final quality of the deliverables.

Figure 5 – Data processing diagram

The following Data Processing Quality Control (DPQC) - **Appendix 3** - procedures and checks will be performed by the UP team while processing the data and preparing three reports:

DP1. Registration Accuracy Report

As part of the process of validating the accuracy of the registration process a Registration Accuracy Report certifying the accuracies of the point cloud registration.

DP2. Visual Data Check Report

Visual checks shall be performed on the raw point cloud data. The UP team will check for items that may have been overlooked or improperly processed. A Visual Data Check Report will be prepared to certify the accuracy of the results of the process. If appropriate, screen shots may be used to help illustrate the findings.

DP3. Model Check Report

A Model Check Report will be prepared by the UP team certifying the accuracies obtained and the overall level of quality achieved in the modeling process. This report will include Model Integrity Checks, Model Control Checks, Interference Checks and Standards Checks

DP3.1 Model integrity checks

Checks shall be performed by the UP team to ensure that the data has no undefined, incorrectly defined or duplicated elements. This is a visual check that is sometimes referred to as a “watertight model”

wherein modeled elements are joined properly and are “tight fitting”. This step may also include comparing the raw point cloud data to the modeled data.

DP3.2 Model control checks

The UP team shall certify that the acquired data’s coordinate system matches the mesh modeled data. As an added check the control points shall be included in the modeled data. Control points will be used as a visual comparison to their location in the model vs. their location in the point cloud data.

DP3.3 Mesh model

The reconstruction software may generate a high-resolution mesh (50 - 30k polygons), which is not suitable for use in BIM software which has trouble handling such huge meshes, therefore it’s necessary to generate a lower resolution for this purpose (*more details submitted on chapters 6.2 File format and specifications of point clouds and mesh models*). The goal is to make the lower resolution mesh look as similar as possible to the high-resolution mesh by generating a normal map using baking tools. Baking tools should be used to transfer high-frequency information (small details) of the high-resolution mesh that are otherwise lost when converting low-resolution meshes to textures. The photogrammetry software provides the decimation process to optimize a mesh- decimate mesh. Decimation process allows defining the number of desired polygons. If the decimation process gives a good result, it can be used as a base to produce the medium/ low-resolution mesh for baking. If the result is not good enough, or if the mesh is too complex, the UP process uses the decimation process to do a medium resolution mesh with (10 – 6k polygons). Both the high resolution and the medium or low-resolution mesh (depending on the decimation process quality) must be exported. The high-resolution mesh will be used as the source for baking the normal maps, and the low or medium resolution mesh can be reworked in 3D modelling software to generate a proper low-resolution mesh used as the destination of the baking. The UP team can create a lower resolution mesh while preserving the details of the high-resolution mesh by generating a normal map with baking tools. The baking tools will transfer high-frequency information from the high-resolution mesh to the low-resolution mesh’s normal map textures. A medium to low-resolution mesh is also exported from the reconstruction software and modified in a 3D software tool to be used as the destination of the baking tools (Retopology and UV layout step). Baking tools are then used to generate textures.

PD3.3 Standard checks

The UP team shall certify that any data format, CAD, BIM or other standards required in the SOW have been met. The UP team will provide a method for demonstrating this. When a model is provided as a deliverable, a mesh model-checking software report may be considered as one acceptable form of showing compliance.

2.4 Phase 4: Deliverables

The UP team will prepare and deliver the Final Deliverables Package. Furthermore, the UP team will summarize the overall results of the project in terms of quality management in this report. The following checklist can be found in **Appendix 4** which outlines all items required to be included in the report.

2.4.1. File Structure and Organization

A clear and well-organized data set will help ensure the success of the project. This structure should be planned out in advance of processing the geometric survey data. All the geometric survey data must be delivered using a particular organizational structure. It is suggested that this structure be used throughout the project by the team. A template of the project folder structure is available for download in the following link:

<https://www.gsa.gov/real-estate/design-construction/3d4d-building-information-modeling/guidelines-for-bim-software/downloads/templates>

2.4.2 File format and specifications of point clouds and mesh models.

The required file formats and specifications are as follows:

Point cloud files: Two separate files or chunks of exterior and interior of the building located on the same coordinate system. All the point clouds must be with color information. The required file format of the must be *.e57* or *.rcp and *.ply.

Mesh polycount and mesh type specification are as follows:

- A Mesh polycount of the original high poly model (50 - 30k polygons) or chunks of the exterior's building case study. This mesh model also consists of the Mesh polycount of the textured model.
- A Medium polycount mesh model or chunks of the exterior's building case study, with a resolution between 10.000.0000 to 6.000.000 faces. The interior part will remain in the point cloud with colour information format as specified above, except from selected parts which will be selected after consideration, where a mesh will be required, separate from the exterior but located in the same coordinate system with resolution up to 1.000.000 faces. All the mesh models will be delivered in *.obj file formats.
- Texture: The output texture size required will be 8K (8921), in tiff, jpg or png format, with alpha channel.

Moreover, it is required that all geometric survey data be delivered in the raw files (original photos or laser scans) and preliminary editing work prior to final model/texture export, such as photo alignment information (photogrammetry workflow), in case of texture reprojection on re-topologized and edited meshes, as well as in ASTM e57format. It is the responsibility of the UP geometric survey working group to convert all data to the ASTM e57 format.

2.4.3 Naming Standards

Clear and concise naming is required to ensure the future use of geometric survey data. The specifics of the naming convention are to be established as part of the BEP and must follow the standards outlined in the Naming Standard.

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Appendix 1- Project Planning template

PP1. Geometrical Data Survey Information

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP1.1 Building Information

Identification number: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Building Name: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Building Location: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Building Address: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Building Type/Use: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Number of floors: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Height of the building: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Levels Above Grade: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Levels Below Grade: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Square Footage of Building: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Phases (construction / modification): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Name & Address of owner: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP1.2 Existing Documentation

Indicate what documentation is available and what file formats

Floor Plans (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Elevations (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Site Plan (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Photographs: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Other: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP1.3 Accessibility and Field Conditions

Protection Information: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Protection date: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Occupied or Vacant? *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Is power available? *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Hazardous Conditions: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP2. Project Objectives

PP2. 1 Statement of Intent

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP2. 2 Level of Accuracy

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP2. 3 Level of Detail

PP2. 3.1 Brief Description of the laser scanning objectives

Table 1 shows a high-level overview of project objectives. Refer *Table 2* for complete element by element explanations.

Objective	Approximate m ²	Coordinate Frame	Deliverable Type	Level of Detail (Documentation)
Typical Exterior Space				
Typical Interior Space				
Typical Construction Verification				
Typical As-Built				

Table 1. Project Primary Objectives Matrix

PP2. 3.1 Brief Description of the geometric survey objectives

[Complete the chart below, adding items as needed. You may also wish to remove unused columns to shorten the table]

Uni. II Class	Element	Typical Exterior Space Scan / Model		Typical Interior Space Scan / Model		Typical Construction Verification Scan		Typical As-Built Scan / Model	
		Scan	Model	Scan	Model	Scan	Model	Scan	Model
A1010	Standard Foundations								
A1020	Special Foundations								
A1030	Slab on Grade								
A2010	Basement Excavation								
A2020	Basement Walls								
B1010	Floor Construction								
B1020	Roof Construction								
B2010	Exterior Walls								
B2020	Exterior Windows								
B2030	Exterior Doors								

B3010	Roof Coverings								
B3020	Roof Openings								
C1010	Partitions								
C1020	Interior Doors								
C1030	Fittings								
C2010	Stair Construction								
C2020	Stair Finishes								
C3010	Wall Finishes								
C3020	Floor Finishes								
C3030	Ceiling Finishes								
D1010	Elevators & Lifts								
D1020	Escalators & Moving Walks								
D1030	Other Conveying Systems								
D2010	Plumbing Fixtures								
D2020	Domestic Water Distribution								
D2030	Sanitary Waste								
D2040	Rain Water Drainage								
D2090	Other Plumbing Systems								
D3010	Energy Supply								
D3020	Heat Generating Systems								
D3030	Cooling Generating Systems								
D3040	Distribution Systems								
D3050	Terminal & Package Units								
D3060	Controls & Instrumentatio n								
D3070	Systems Testing & Balancing								
D3090	Other HVAC Systems & Equipment								
D4010	Sprinklers								

D4020	Standpipes								
D4030	Fire Protection Specialties								
D4090	Other Fire Protection Systems								
D5010	Electrical Service & Distribution								
D5020	Lighting and Branch Wiring								
D5030	Communications & Security								
D5090	Other Electrical Systems								
E1010	Commercial Equipment								
E1020	Institutional Equipment								
E1030	Vehicular Equipment								
E1090	Other Equipment								
E2010	Fixed Furnishings								
E2020	Movable Furnishings								
F1010	Special Structures								
F1020	Integrated Construction								
F1030	Special Construction Systems								
F1040	Special Facilities								
F1050	Special Controls & Instrumentation								
F2010	Building Elements Demolition								
F2020	Hazardous Components Abatement								
G1010	Site Clearing								

G1020	Site Demolition & Relocations								
G1030	Site Earthwork								
G1040	Hazardous Waste Remediation								
G2010	Roadways								
G2020	Parking Lots								
G2030	Pedestrian Paving								
G2040	Site Development								
G2050	Landscaping								
G3010	Water Supply & Distribution Systems								
G3020	Sanitary Sewer Systems								
G3030	Storm Sewer Systems								
G3040	Heating Distribution								
G3050	Cooling Distribution								
G3060	Fuel Distribution								
G3090	Other Civil/Mechanical Utilities								
G4010	Electrical Distribution								
G4020	Site Lighting								
G4030	Site Communications & Security								
G4090	Other Electrical Utilities								
G5010	Service Tunnels								
G5090	Other Site Systems & Equipment								

Table 2. Object Level Requirements Matrix

PP3. On-site schedule

Plan view layouts highlighting proposed instrument locations and areas of coverage.

3d Scanning

[add specific information on the case study building]

Aerial and Terrestrial Photogrammetry paths

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP4. Equipment

3d Scan -type and Model

[add specific information on the case study building]

Camera for terrestrial photogrammetry - model and lenses

[add specific information on the case study building]

Camera for aerial photogrammetry - model and lenses

[add specific information on the case study building]

Rectified photography properties

[add specific information on the case study building]

Property	Value
Dimensions	
ISO speed	
F-stop	
Exposure time	
Flash mode	
Focal Length	
Output	
Field of view (FOV)	

Colour Checker Setup

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP5. Data Acquisition Plan

Methodology

[add specific information on the case study building]

Data density

[add specific information on the case study building]

Survey plan

[add specific information on the case study building]

Survey control

[add specific information on the case study building]

Targets

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP6. Data Processing

Registration Reports

[add specific information on the case study building]

Statistical comparison of point cloud and control points

[add specific information on the case study building]

Model check reports

[add specific information on the case study building]

Standards report

[add specific information on the case study building]

PP7. Reference Materials

[List all EXISTING information to be provided to the 3D image servicer for reference, such as existing building documentation, building preservation plans, environmental assessments/EIS reports, and/or other relevant surveys and studies etc.]

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Appendix 2- Data Acquisition Report

DA1 Survey Instrument Calibration

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA2 Survey Control

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3 Survey plan

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.1 Site Conditions

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.2 Location of geometric survey equipment

[add specific information on the case study building]

Useful Range

[add specific information on the case study building]

Point Density

[add specific information on the case study building]

Positioning

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.3 Targets

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.4 Color checker

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.5 Scale metric

[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.4 Detailed textures

[add specific information on the case study building]

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Appendix 3- Data Processing Template

DP1 Registration Accuracy

Building Name and location: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Date: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Author of report: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Describe the method use to perform the registration: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Registration results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Does the registration fall within the range of acceptable error?

[add specific information on the case study building]

DP2 Visual Data Check Report

Describe the method use to perform the visual data check

[add specific information on the case study building]

Visual data check results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Corrective action taken (if any): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

DP3 Model Check

[add specific information on the case study building]

DP3.1 Model integrity

Provide information that there are no undefined elements

[add specific information on the case study building]

Provide information that there are no incorrectly defined elements

[add specific information on the case study building]

Provide information that there are no duplicated elements

[add specific information on the case study building]

Provide information that elements are right fitting or “water tight”

[add specific information on the case study building]

Describe method used to perform the model integrity checks

[add specific information on the case study building]

Present model integrity results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Corrective action taken (if any): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

DP3.2 Model control checks

Provide information that that model coordinates match the acquired data coordinates

[add specific information on the case study building]

Provide information that of inclusion and proper alignment of the control points in the model

[add specific information on the case study building]

Describe method use to perform the model control checks

[add specific information on the case study building]

Present model control checks results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Corrective action taken: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Name of the individual who performed the model control checks

[add specific information on the case study building]

DP3.3 Mesh Models

Mesh Model polycount in high quality (polygons number)

[add specific information on the case study building]

Mesh Model polycount in medium quality (polygons number)

[add specific information on the case study building]

Mesh Model polycount in low quality (polygons number)

[add specific information on the case study building]

Texture resolution

[add specific information on the case study building]

DP3.4 Standard checks

Provide information that any data format, cad, BIM or other standards required in the SOW have been met: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Describe method to perform standard checks: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Corrective action taken (if any): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Appendix 4: Project Data Deliverable Report

PDD1. Project Delivery Approach

[Provide a summary explanation of overall sequencing of how the project and the required 3D imaging effort are broken down into various parts, if applicable. Explain how the 3D imaging efforts will integrate into the larger design project and the expectation for support after the initial data is collected.]

PDD2. Input Data

PDD2.1 Laser Scanner point cloud

Scans quality

[add specific information on the case study building]

Number of inputs

[add specific information on the case study building]

Type and number markers

Number of control markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Number of test markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Point cloud color mode

Colorized yes|no

Point cloud density

[add specific information on the case study building]

Point cloud coordinate system

Aligned with the coordinate system yes|no

Modified point cloud data

Alignment yes|no

Cleaning yes|no

Density reduction yes|no

Other *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Point cloud output format

*e57 yes|no

.rcs or *.rcp yes|no

*ply yes|no

PDD2.2 Photogrammetry point cloud

Source

Camera yes|no

Drone yes|no

Other yes|no

Source quality

Model of camera: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Focal length: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

ISO speed: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

F-stop: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Exposure time: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Flash mode: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Output: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Type and number markers

Number of control markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Number of test markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Pre-processing of RAW images

Lens correction: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Distortion: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Count of registered images

[add specific information on the case study building]

Count of aligned images

[add specific information on the case study building]

Point cloud density

[add specific information on the case study building]

Point cloud color mode

Colorized yes|no

Point cloud coordinate system

Aligned with the coordinate system yes|no

Modified point cloud data

Alignment yes|no

Cleaning yes|no

Density reduction yes|no

Other *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Point cloud output format

*e57 yes|no
.rcs or *.rcp yes|no
*ply yes|no

PDD2.3 Mesh model

Mesh polycount of original high poly model

[add specific information on the case study building]

Mesh polycount of textured model

[add specific information on the case study building]

Mesh polycount of decimated models

[add specific information on the case study building]

Mesh color mode

Colorized yes|no

Texture size

8k yes|no
Alpha channel yes|no

Mesh model output format

*obj yes|no
*fbx yes|no
*other

Texture format

*tiff
*jpeg
*png

Mesh model coordinate system

Aligned with the coordinate system yes|no

PDD2.4 2D drawings

Annotated topographical survey yes|no
Annotated plans yes|no
Elevations and section yes|no
Construction details yes|no
Other *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PDD2.5 Other sources

[add specific information on the case study building]

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Appendix 5: Detail textures

Below is a short description of the main technical terms based on the Glossary of technical terms. ¹

Arcade: series of arches on columns or piers attached to or detached from the wall of a building

Arch: load transmitting structural form designed to span openings. Consists of the wedge-shaped stone blocks or bricks arranged in a radical pattern supported by walls, columns or piers on either side. The shape and character of an arch depends on where the center or centers of the radii to set it out are placed. Common types of arch include: semi-circular or Roman (one-centred); segmental (one-centred); gothic or pointed (two-centred); three-centred or suppressed; Tudor (four-centred).

Ashlar: open or covered (top lit) courtyard in the centre of a building serving as hall or assembly space.

Baluster: Vertical support or bar to a handrail or coping in a balustrade, of square, cylindrical, turned or ornamental shape.

Balustrade: row of balusters supporting the handrail of a stair or coping to a parapet.

Bay window: a projecting window construction of rectangular, faceted or curved shape.

Beam: horizontal structural member supported at each end by walls, columns or piers.

Bracket: projecting structural member designed to support weight above; is generally in the form of scrolls, volutes or simpler oblong shape.

Cantilever: beam, floor slab, canopy or other structural member, built into a projecting from a wall or building structure without other support along its length.

Canopy: roof-like element above a doorway, window, pulpit or altar which is cantilevered, suspended or supported by brackets or columns.

Capital: the top element or head of a column, shaft, pilaster or pier; of architectural or decorative treatment which is distinctive in style.

Casement window: a window of which the opening glazed frames (or "lights") are hinged at the sides.

Cill (or sill): projecting member at the bottom of a window or door, shaped to throw off rainwater.

Cloister: covered passages around a courtyard to a building or group of buildings, usually arcaded and designed to provide shelter from the elements. Originated in ecclesiastical and collegiate architecture.

Coffers: sunken panels formed in ceiling, vaults and domes to lighten the construction and for decorative effect.

Colonnade: row of columns, usually in front of a building, carrying an entablature and support a roofed passageway or porch, sometimes serving as a portico or entrance way into the building.

Column: vertical support of cylindrical or polygonal shape; in classical architecture sitting on a base and terminated by a load-spreading capital at the top.

Console: classical bracket of ogee shape incorporating volutes at top and bottom terminations.

¹ The Oxford Dictionary of Architecture by James Curl and Sir Banister Fletcher's History of Architecture, 20th edition published by the Architectural Press, U.K

Coping: capping at the top of a wall or parapet to throw the water off, variously in stone, brick, metal or concrete.

Corbel: projecting block of stone or other material from the face of a wall or the top of a door or window opening, designed to support a beam, roof truss, lintel or other building element.

Cornice: classical feature consisting of a projecting moulded horizontal top of an entablature or top of building.

Crenellation: indentations on upper part of parapet of a building, originally for defensive purposes.

Cupola: hemi- spherical or bowl- shaped vault or dome on top of a building or structure.

Dado: part of a pedestal between its base and its cornice lower portion of a wall which has a different treatment to the top eg. Wooden paneling or marble cladding.

Dentil: row of small blocks or “teeth “set closely apart under a classical cornice.

Doorway: Round arched, rectangular entrance into a building or room usually with rectangular shape surroundings.

Entablature: Classical architecture term, refers to the horizontal elements or divisions carried above the columns or pilasters, viz. architrave, frieze and cornice.

Fanlight: glazed opening above a door.

Fascia: band with plain vertical face e.g. board at eaves of a building or over a shop front.

Finial: the top part of a pinnacle, spire or other rooftop feature; usually of decorative form.

Fluting: vertical channeling on the face of a column, pier, pilaster or other building element.

Foils: small arc opening in Gothic tracery e.g. trefoil (three foils)

Fretwork: cut-out band like ornament in a wooden, metal or marble plank or slab.

Frieze: horizontal band in a classical entablature between the cornice and architrave.

Gable: triangular part of a wall enclosing lines of sloping roof pediment in Classical architecture.

Gargoyle: water spout used to drain roofs without guttering or down pipes, often treated decoratively.

Giant order: Classical columns, pilaster or piers rising more than one storey.

Hood: projecting cover or canopy over a doorway, window or fireplace.

Jetty: finishing of joints in masonry or brickwork while the mortar is still soft.

Keystone: A centrally placed decorative stone in the center of the doorway top.

Lancet arch: sharply pointed above a doorway or window opening.

Lantern: structure rising above a roof in the form of a cylindrical or polygonal tower with glazed sides to give light below.

Lattice: grid or framework of wooden or metal bars or rods in structural or decorative form.

Loggia: a roofed over gallery located within an open arcade or colonnade, usually on an upper floor of a building.

Machicolation: projecting wall or parapet in a fortification with floor openings to shoot down or drop stones or boiling oil on enemy below.

Mullion: vertical element or member which divides a window into lights.

Niche: hollowed out recess in a wall to hold a statue, urn, ornament or shelves.

Parapet: low wall or barrier at the top of a roof, balcony, veranda, bridge or terrace.

Pedestal: support for a column or statue consisting of a base and cornice.

Pediment: classical element of triangular, segmental or broken form with raking cornices above a entablature.

Peristyle: colonnades surrounding a building or court.

Pilaster: shallow depth rectangular feature projecting from a wall surface, resembling a pillar with classical detailing.

Pillar: freestanding slender pier.

Pinnacle: ornamental feature terminating a spire, turret, buttress parapet top or other external building feature.

Plaque: slab of stone, marble, metal terracotta or any kind of tablet inscribed and affixed to a wall or other part of structure.

Plinth: lowest square part of a column base projecting base of a building.

Podium: a continuous pedestal

Portal: entrance doorway or gateway of monumental character.

Portico: roofed colonnaded structure forming an entrance or vestibule to a building.

Quoins: corner stones at the angles of a building.

Roundel: small circular window deep circular niche containing a bust. Also referred to as bulls-eye or oculus.

Rubble: rough stones of irregular shapes and sizes used in the construction of walls, resulting in fairly large mortar joints which are plugged with inset small stones (gallets).

Shaft: portion of column between base and capital.

Shutter: hinged, rolling or sliding opening timber or metal leaves or curtains used for security and weather protection to windows and doors. May be solid, perforated or louvered.

Stanchion: cast iron or steel vertical support.

Tetrasyle: frontal of temple or portico consisting of four columns.

Tracery: ornamental geometric pattern work within upper part of Gothic window.

Trefoil: tracery element of three foils in Gothic window.

Truglyph: incised stone block within a Doric frieze incorporating V-shaped channels.

Truss: structural framework of timber or metal spanning a space.

Tympanum: triangular surface bounded by the sloping and horizontal cornices of a classical pediment, space between the arch and lintel of a doorway or window.

Vault: arched stone, brick or concrete structure over a building.

Veranda: external open gallery around a building whose roof is supported on columns or posts to provide protection from the elements, also used as an outdoor living space. Found in tropical, sub-tropical and Mediterranean colonial buildings.

Vestibule: enclose or semi- enclose space in front of the main entrance to a building, a hall or entrance lobby between entrance door and interior rooms.

Voussoirs: wedge- shaped stone blocks or rubbed bricks forming the structure of an arch or vault.

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